

Effects of Guided Inquiry- based Learning and Teaching Approach on Students' Confidence, Motivation and Communication Skills in an Introductory Computer Programming Course

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Abstract

Entry-level students joining the university find the sudden transition from the familiar schooling environment quite challenging. This is very evident among the students who enroll for difficult courses such as introduction to programming. Students' confidence, motivation and communication skills are major factors that determine their eventual success in such courses. The traditional teacher-centered approach to teaching does not address this problem. This study aimed to find the effects of teaching entry-level students doing an introductory computer programming course in a South African university through Guided Inquiry Learning (GIL) approach on their confidence, motivation, and communication skills. GIL is an active, learner-centered collaborative learning and teaching approach. This study was located in a pragmatic paradigm using a mixed-methods approach. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected from 19 students who voluntarily participated in the study and were analysed using descriptive statistical methods and thematic analysis respectively. The study found that the GIL approach had a significant positive impact on the students' confidence, motivation and communication skills. Students were motivated and confident to continue studying the advanced programming courses.

Introduction

Computer programming (often called programming) is the process of developing and implementing various sets of instructions to enable a computer to do a certain task. Programming is an important course taught in higher education institutions as part of the curriculum of the undergraduate programmes in Computer Science (CS) and Information Technology (IT) disciplines. Programming is one of the most feared courses by first year students with high failure rate (Bennedsen & Caspersen, 2007; Chetty & Westhuizen, 2015; Derus & Ali, 2012; Gomes & Mendes, 2007; Pillay, 2003; Watson & Li, 2014). Low pass rates in Introduction to programming have been common for decades (Cheah, 2020). Majority of the first time learners find computer programming difficult to understand and pass (Bergin & Reilly, 2005; Derus & Ali, 2012; Kinnunen & Malmi, 2008; Robins, Rountree & Rountree, 2003; Robins, 2019; Roddan, 2002; Schoeman, 2015; Tinto, 1975).

Entry-level programmers are often seen to be having difficulty in grasping the foundation level programming concepts early in their studies, leading to grief and frustration and ultimately surrender (Shuhaidan et al., 2009). They often carry this conceptual baggage and that hinders their ability to understand concepts in their further levels of studies. Understanding of programming poses many challenges for first year students, since a large number enter CS/IT qualifications with little or no prior knowledge (Falkner & Munro, 2009). Programming is problem solving intensive (Bosse & Gerosa, 2017). Learners need to move away from the conventional way of learning they have been practicing in the (familiar) school environment. The main problem faced by students in learning to program is taking previous knowledge and adopting a learning approach that goes beyond memorizing explicit knowledge to construct the tacit knowledge necessary to apply and transfer the concept of domain to a new situation (Affleck and Smith, 1999). This poses a new challenge to the learners who start a programming course in universities. They are coming from a familiar academic setting where they were studying topics/subjects that were familiar, comfortable and were studying for some years (Jenkins, 2002). They have been practicing tried, tested and trusted learning skills at school level. They are confronted with totally new topics that demand more than those habitual learning skills at university. This poses a critical challenge to them. According to Jenkins (2002), some less obvious skills such as life skills can also pose a challenge to the entry-level learners as they will be facing some of the most challenging materials in their programming course in their first years of university life. Some later studies have concurred with this assessment (Bain & Barnes, 2014; Gomes et al., 2012). This is the time when they are going through a transition as they adapt to the all-new way of life and study at a non-familiar environment of a university. Individual domains including personal factors may influence the successful outcome of students learning to program. A student's motivation in engaging in

activities pertaining to learn programming and his/her capabilities to complete them can better describe these personal factors (Carbone et al., 2009). The difficulties they find in learning to program in their early days of university life affect students' motivation level. Lack of skills affects students' confidence and motivation in a negative direction (Carbone et al., 2009; Rahman et al., 2018; Settle et al., 2014). According to Kinnunen and Malmi(2006), low level of motivation is one of the major reasons why students drop out of IT courses. Without motivation, there may not be any reason to 'succeed' in programming. Entry-level students may have the potential intellectual capacity to create programs, but that in itself may not be enough to learn programming successfully. As Zimmerman (1995) observes, even though students may possess the intellectual capacity, if they are poorly motivated, they may still fail to learn to program. Course assessment results may not reflect the true ability of learners, if they are not motivated enough to do well as was confirmed by Teague (2009) through the study conducted to determine the extent to which the personal factors such as motivation and confidence affects students learning to program. Traditional passive teaching and learning approach might not be enough to motivate and instill confidence among entry level students in learning programming. Hence, the reason for this study which explored if teaching an introductory programming course with the active, constructivist Guided Inquiry Learning (GIL) approach has had any effects on students' confidence, motivation and communication skills as compared to those taught with traditional approaches. At the selected South African university where this study was conducted, Development Software 1 (DEV1120) is an introductory programming course offered at entry-level of a three-year undergraduate qualification specializing in Information Technology. The average failure rate in the past five years for this course was 51.44%. The purpose of this course is to equip learners with a solid understanding of the basic principles of programming that apply to all computer programming languages. Though this course does not involve in teaching any specific programming language, Visual Basic (VB.net) console application is used for practical purposes in the latter half of the academic year.

Literature Review

Students' Motivation, Confidence and Communication Skills and Their Academic Performance

The general definition of motivation as indicated by Breen (1999) is "the nature of an individual's internal forces and the extent to which they define external goals and direct the individual towards them" (p.1). A study conducted by Round (2005) showed that students who achieved everyday academic motivation liked their courses, have self-academic confidence and have understanding of the academic environment. It is argued by Dooley (2004) that motivation affects students' academic success, confidence and the level of communication among them. The two common types of motivations are intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is about the behaviour performed in order to experience joy and happiness, such as the interest of studying a particular course (Winn, 2002). Extrinsic motivation is about performing a behaviour as a means to achieve (to receive a final incentive) such as to pass a course (Winn, 2002). Mäkinen et al. (2004) indicated that motivation is linked to the commitment that students put in a subject. This could be through in class or out of class socialisation among students. Motivation brings in confidence in students and the required joy and interest.

Self-confidence is "the assurance that a person has in his or her own abilities, towards conceptualized in the academic areas" (Jones & Thomas, 2001, p.3). The Oxford English Dictionary 2018 explains confidence as "a feeling of self-assurance arising from an appreciation of one's own abilities or qualities" ("Confidence", 2018). But confidence differs between individuals in the same situation (Sander et al, 2000). Levels of confidence differ for people in different situations. Sander et al. observed that one can be highly confident in a familiar setting, and at the same time lose confidence in an unfamiliar and challenging environment (2000). Academic confidence is conceptualised as being how students are different in having a 'strong belief and firm trust' of what their institution has to offer (Jackson, 2003). Academic confidence is based on four sources: mastery, vicarious experience, verbal persuasion and physiological states (Round, 2005). The researcher further argues that academic confidence, therefore, is proposed as an interlink between one's inherent capabilities, his/her learning techniques and the resources afforded by university (Round, 2005). This means that students who are having academic confidence are likely to interact and communicate with one another more, as they understand the role and significance of communication for academic achievements. This leads to a further discussion on communication.

Since in most cases learners in a university come from different high schools with different background, it is clear that communication becomes a challenge. In most rural schools of South Africa, English is used as a second language yet is the main language of communication at universities. Communication is a vital part of our daily routines (Bygate, 1987). Through communication, students learn from each other and acquire different skills, their confidence will grow and, become more motivated (Dörnyei&Thurrell, 1994). When students have communicative competence, they grow in academic confidence. Therefore, communicative strategies at universities should be targeted towards increasing students' competence and activities that they do. The terms motivation, confidence and communication are well linked and lead to one goal for students- success; especially in their early stages at universities. Students become more comfortable and confident to interact and enjoy learning if they are exposed to good communication platforms.

Approaches to computing education

Science including Computer Science (and programming) is traditionally taught deductively. Typically, the instructor begins with theories (syntax and semantics) and then progresses (in most cases) to the application of those theories. Programmers are required to do much more than recalling the syntax and semantics, substituting values and finding answers. In their daily operations, students will be required to communicate fluently, observe and analyse complex problem situations and be able to work in a group. Universities should aim to develop such skills among the learners for them to become industry-ready once they graduate. To achieve this, a combination of teaching and learning methods accommodating different learning styles are necessary. Several authors have reported on the inadequacy of chalk-and-talk approach in enhancing understanding as it only promotes passive learning (Betihavas et al., 2016; Brandsteidl et al., 2012; Giannakos & Vlamos, 2010; Hake, 1998; O'Flaherty & Phillips, 2015; Saeed, 2018). According to Gibson (2002), a constructivist view of learning and a consequent move away from the traditional chalk-and-talk teaching methods will benefit the student through recognition and development of his/her multiple intelligence. He goes on to say that, "traditional teaching methods are ineffective and, in any case, neither encourage nor measure student understanding even when teachers think otherwise" (p. 466).

Several authors have reported on the inadequacy of passive learning (Cremasco et al., 2016; Magana et al., 2018; Michel et al., 2009; Riley & Ward, 2015; Smith, 2014; Stewart, 2014). Passive learning is likely to fail since each student in a classroom constructs new knowledge in a different manner as each of them brings different cognitive frameworks into the classroom (Ben-Ari, 1998). He further observed that learning must be active and knowledge is constructed through guidance by the teacher and feedback from other students.

Guided Inquiry Learning (GIL)

GIL follows a form of collaborative inductive learning approach. The strategies in GIL include, among others, learning teams who participate in intra- and inter-learner interactions besides lecturer-learner interactions, linking theory and practical information cementing skills and problem solving strategies, scaffolding information, blended learning by integrating both traditional and technology-assisted learning, inquiry activities such as initiating investigations, gathering data, and critiquing evidence to come up with evidence-based solutions. Through an empirical study conducted among the students in an introductory programming course, McKinney and Denton (2006) observed that, exposing students to collaborative learning environments at their early stage of learning resulted in the benefits among the students such as deeper learning, developing skills wanted by industry, higher retention, higher achievement, higher course success rates, higher interest and higher sense of belonging. These benefits were enjoyed by all students but were important for first year students who were at risk of leaving the discipline. Falkner and Munro (2009) applied a range of collaborative learning techniques within an introductory CS (programming) course in the School of CS, University of Adelaide, Australia to address specifically problem solving skills over a three year period. Their attempt to integrate collaborative learning activities with cooperative problem solving processes, involving students in small groups working through a set of small problems impacted positively on the social aspect of the course and the problem solving skills. Students were able to quickly develop a peer group. They observed increased student confidence and perception of ability, and increased student ability to complete problem solving activities. They further observed that the students felt more comfortable in asking questions and arguing their positions in their groups than they felt in larger classes.

Theoretical Framework

A framework entails concepts put together based on their relevance, and the research problems that provides a frame of reference for the research (Devi, Das, Das, & Khandelwal, 2017). The theoretical framework for this study was based on Vygotsky's social constructivism theory. Learning takes place first on an interpersonal level through interaction with others, that is then transformed into an intrapersonal one (Vygotski, 1978). The notion, Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) which was introduced by Vygotski explains how learning and development takes place. Vygotsky (1978) defines ZPD as "the distance between the actual development level as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers" (p. 86). The ZPD informs the role of educators, education technology and peers in the learning processes. Teachers provide adult guidance necessary to lift learner competences from actual developmental mode to a higher level of capability. Social constructivist theory proposes that in order for learning to take place, students must be active participants in their own learning. Through conversations and exchange of ideas with teachers and other students, students become active participants and that help them reach new horizons of understanding (Harkness, 2009). Learning does not occur for an individual learner alone but it is influenced by the peers and/or the teacher. Social constructivism theory acknowledges the importance of being in a social group (learning environment) and thus makes the foundation for this study.

Research Methodology

The study used a mixed method approach as it promotes integration of both quantitative and qualitative research strategies (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). The research paradigm which provides a world view of the study used was pragmatism. Pragmatism lets the researcher the application of both qualitative and quantitative data depending on the objectives of the study. The correlation of both the qualitative and quantitative data assisted the researcher to understand the effect of GIL on students' soft skills.

49 students enrolled for the introductory programming course (DEV1120) in a South African university formed the population of this study. Out of this enrolled number of students, 20 of them voluntarily agreed to participate in the research and they formed the experimental group and the remaining 29 students formed the control group. One, out of the 20 students from the experimental group dropped out of the course and the entire programme. This made the effective sample 19 for the experimental group. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the university where this study was conducted. Results of the four mandatory summative assessments and the final summative assessment (examination) formed part of the quantitative data for this study. Focus group interviews with semi-structured, open-ended questions were conducted to collect the qualitative data. The interview questions were designed to gather qualitative data detailing the learner experience in their own words. Data analysis include grouping and summarizing information to establish meaning. Quantitative and Qualitative data were analyzed by way of using descriptive statistical methods for the former and thematic analysis for the latter.

Research Process

Both the control and experimental groups had same number of contact hours per week. Control group was taught using the traditional (chalk-and-talk) teaching approach while the experimental group was taught using the GIL approach. The GIL classroom was designed in such a way that it promoted team work. The classroom consisted of round tables that could accommodate up to five students. Students were divided into groups of four to five students. Arranging the classroom in this manner enabled students to communicate effectively in their groups and collaborate easily on tasks. A typical GIL class session started with the lecturer introducing new topics followed by doing an example programming problem with students applying GIL principles. The GIL steps followed included analysis of the problem by asking students questions (inquiring), on and about the problem scenario. Students were also encouraged to ask questions themselves. Answers to these questions make the problem solving process more understandable or that may lead to other questions. Following-up on all these questions by students themselves eventually led them towards the answers/solutions to the given problem. Once the example problem/question is completed, the lecturer then provided new programming problems to the groups. Students who were seated in groups of four to five (collectively) were required to formulate the programming solution using GIL approach. Students in their own groups, attempted to solve the given problem through discussions and asking pertinent questions/inquiries between each other. Lecturer walked around the class, listening to these group discussions and provided guidance to individual groups where required by asking thought provoking questions thus acting only as a facilitator/guide to them. Towards the end of the class session, students were given take-home programming problems to solve on their own in the form of home works.

Findings

Findings based on Quantitative data

Table 1. Demographic information of students

Variable		Experimental group		Control Group	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	M	11	57.89	16	55.17
	F	8	42.10	13	44.52
Students' Home Language	English	0	0	0	0
	Xosa	18	94.73	29	100
	Afrikaans	1	5.26	0	0
Total		19	100	29	100

Table 1 indicated that though number of male students were slightly higher than that of the female students, there no significant differences in gender distribution in both experimental and control groups. For majority of the students, Xosa was their home (first) language (94.73 and 100 percentages respectively for experimental and

control groups). This further indicated that English, the language of instruction at this university was a second language for all participating students.

Following findings were based on data obtained through the assessments given to students throughout the duration of the course DEV1120.

Figure 1: Percentage pass rate for the assessments and the final result – experimental versus control groups.

Overall performance in all the assessments of the students under the experimental group was better than those under the control group. Students final achievement results show a welcoming 37.8% difference between the groups taught with GIL approach and traditional approach in favour of the experimental group.

Figure 2: Mean Scores (%) of assessments - Experimental versus control groups

The experimental group was generally performing well as the mean scores for the experimental group on all assessments were all higher than that of the control group. Figure 2 shows that students taught using GIL performed slightly higher (65.30) than the control group (63.97). Similarly, test three mean scores show that the experiment group performed (56.21) better than the control group (46.34). In addition, findings from test two and four show that the experimental group performed significantly better than the control group. For example, the mean score of test two marks for the experimental group is 57.4 as compared to that of the control group

34.07. Similarly, test four showed a significantly high mean score for experimental group (58.32) as compared to that of the control group (33.79). These results show that GIL collectively improved the performance of students with minimum outliers as students help each other understand the subject during the learning process. This argument is supported by the number of students who failed in class tests. For example, none (0%) of the students in the experimental group failed test one as compared to four (13.8%) from the control group. Only one (5.3%) student from the experimental group failed test two as compared to twenty (69.0%) from the control group. Twelve (41.4%) students from the control group failed test three as compared to three (15.8%) from the experimental group. Lastly, nearly half of the students (48.3%) failed test four from the control group as compared to one (5.3%) from the experimental group.

As shown through Figure 1, the overall pass rates of GIL and traditional learning approach were 89% and 52% respectively for introductory programming course. Watson and Li (2014) reported that the global pass rate for programming courses as 67.7% which is significantly lower than the one found for the experimental group of this study. Furthermore, the same authors reported that South Africa's overall failure rate as approximately 45% for the programming courses. The failure rate of the control group as found through this study (48%) is close to their findings and hence confirmatory of the findings of Watson and Li (2014).

Findings based on Qualitative data

Focus group interviews were conducted with the students who were part of the experimental group to gain more insight on their experience in learning the introductory programming course through GIL approach. The collected data were coded and thematically analysed. The following themes emerged from the responses of students:

Theme 1: GIL Generated self-belief and confidence among students to write computer programs that work.

Subjective personal experience which contributes towards students' level of confidence does play a major role in their decision to continue with the CS/IT degree (McDowell et al., 2006). At the end of the academic year, almost of all the students who were part of the experimental group indicated that they believed in themselves, in their own abilities to write computer programs that work. They have achieved the confidence in writing programs, which is the essential ingredient any student should have in order to be successful. They indicated that the GIL approach had enabled them to gain this confidence. The following responses in verbatim proves this:

FG1 P1: *I think I can do it. I can do programming. I haven't faced any problem that I can't solve at the moment in programming, but I'm not saying I know everything but then again, I haven't faced a problem that I can't solve.*

FG1 P3: *Based on the class works, tests and everything that we have done so far, yes, I can do it*

FG2 P1: *I can say sir; I can write the program that works. Because, with the skills that I have now with those group sessions, yes, I can*

FG2 P2: *I tell you because the lecturer taught me like this, and I gained skills from groups, peers. So the skills that I have I can apply them. So I can write programs*

FG3 P1: *we know we can because we are doing it. We do it in different ways. Students know, do it in different groups.*

FG3 P4: *And I know I can do (program). And now we know that we have a lecturer who communicates with us. He would let you write the program and now we are confident enough to say. Because we know that he didn't do it for us, but we did it ourselves, and just helped and guided here and there. So that's why we can say that, we actually have no problem.*

FG4 P1: *I am confident that I can write programs that run.*

Over the years' studies have found that entry-level students lack in confidence because their attempts to write computer programs fail often. GIL approach in teaching Introductory Programming has given the students the confidence and self-belief that they can successfully write computer programs.

Theme 2: Built strong foundation

The major aim of any introductory course is to build a strong foundation among students in the specific field of study and create a sense of confidence to continue learning/growing in the same field (McDowell et al., 2006). Studies have shown that learning difficulties associated with Introductory Programming courses are a major contributing factor for many entry-level students choosing not to continue with programmes in CS and other cognate fields (Costa et al., 2017; Koulouri et al., 2015; Sheard & Hagan, 1998; Watson & Li, 2014). Students who participated in this study overwhelmingly acknowledged and believed that they had attained a strong foundation in computer programming through this course. They believed that they could nurture their skills in

programming through the strong foundation that they achieved currently. This is evident from the responses in verbatim of the students as given below:

FG1 P1: *I have learned the basics - yes – now, like the foundation is there – it's going to be stable. Now I just need to learn more and you know finish everything.*

FG1 P4: *Now, I can weigh my ability as a programmer. The basics are there and I can tackle to do a programme, ...and with the basics that I got in programming, for sure, I can tackle doing the future programming course.*

FG2 P4: *I can say at this stage of study; I have sound background.*

FG3 P2: *First year is the beginning. Teaching up the basics, and I think what the most important thing is to know the basics, and you can make anything from there. I think we got the basic side strong. Strong basics we have, therefore we can learn anything else, that would make programming easier once you know the basics.*

FG3 P3: *We have got some strong background of programming. So for like for example if I have to learn C++ or Java next year, I will understand better from what I learned through the group work and my lecturer this year.*

Theme 3: Grew in confidence to express themselves in front of others

GIL approach and the group sessions enabled students to gain confidence in themselves and as a result, they believe they are able to stand in front of others and express themselves. Following student responses in verbatim asserts this view:

FG1 P3: *GIL sessions helps in terms of confidence, because in terms of confidence, being confident about what you think about that particular thing that we are doing and in terms of debating... I have learned to stand up for something that I have said.*

FG1 P1: *So, socializing with people makes you learn more and makes you more comfortable. ... you feel less pressure, more confident. and yeah and when you are in your group obviously it's gonna be a competition for everyone...then you like give your opinion and learn to argue your opinion. So you like eventually get strong in with giving your own opinion with others.*

FG2 P5: *But the way that this group thing had helped us, that everyone became confident in themselves, and they were able to project themselves, were able to interact when there is a discussion and they were able to..like, how can I put this.*

FG2 P2: *I prefer reading than talking. these group discussions helped me a lot. Because now, I have gained confidence, I can talk with people and collaborate with them.*

FG3 P4: *Also then to be confident, because you said that the answer is like this, they would ask questions how did you go about it to find certain answer, so you have to be confident explaining your views to them so that you get the feedback so that you can interact and explain how you get to the result.*

FG4 P3: *So in future, I can speak in front of many people. So confidence.*

It is evident from these responses that, that they were able to express themselves in front of others and even learned to defend their arguments. These are critical skills they will require to be successful in their future prospective workplaces

Theme 4: Improved problem solving skills

Entry-level students are required to master their problem solving skills in order to be successful in Introductory Programming courses (Lishinski et al., 2016; McCracken et al., 2001). Studies have shown that failure to acquire these skills at the early stage of their university life force them to drop (Morgado& Barbosa, 2012; Yadin, 2011). Students have indicated that GIL approach improved their problem solving skills and gave them confidence in continuing with the programme. Assessments made through the following sub-themes such as 'GIL helped in understanding the problem domain better', 'improved analytical skills' and 'group sessions assisted student while doing home works alone' are clear indicators that the GIL has improved substantially students' overall problem solving skills.

Sub-theme 4.1: GIL helped in understanding the problem domain better

Majority of the students have indicated that GIL sessions have assisted them in decomposing the complexity of the questions and the problem scenario through different views expressed of the scenario by way of peer discussions. This is evident through their verbatim responses as given below:

FG3 P4: *Before there was Inquiry learning, we didn't approach the problem, I myself, I didn't approach the problem, I just look at the question and attack it. But after this GIL, I learned the approach of approaching a problem.*

FG3 P3: *When you are solving a problem.... first you have to read and understand the question before you try to do anything. If you don't, the chance is that you may answer something else. Now we discuss between ourselves and clarify issues in the problem.*

FG4 P1: *There is like different minds over here. So the way she understands the problem, is different from the way I understand the problem. So with me in a group, we try and break it down. Obviously she is gonna tell me something I didn't understand and I gonna say the part I understand. And in that way we gonna find a way for us to tackle the problem.*

Sub-theme 4.2: GIL improved students' analytical skills

One of the critical skills required in mastering problem solving is the ability to critically analyse the problem scenario. Majority of the students appreciated the collaborative active environment created through GIL sessions and how it improved their analytical skills. This is evident through their responses as given below:

FG1 P1: *When you are on your own, you are just given a problem and you just pre-assume that maybe it needs this and that and then you just do it the way you think is correct. But when you are in a group like, we analyse it better and we try to figure it out what is more appropriate way solve the particular problem. Then we came up with different ideas, vary them and choose the correct one.*

FG1 P2: *When we are in our groups we analyse problems and try to come up with different ways to solve this problem.*

FG2 P4: *When we are there as a group, if one not understands the certain part, ask others to explain to him or her, then I see that I made a mistake when I explain it, then we try and analyse the problem thoroughly, and broke it down to smaller pieces, then solve it.*

Sub-theme 4.3: Group session experience assisted students while doing their home works alone

Students used their group session experiences and approaches when they were doing their home works. The questions they asked and were being asked during the group sessions worked as a 'guide' on how to analyse the problem. It was evident that they learned to approach a problem scenario by systematically questioning themselves to understand and analyse the problem to get to (even) alternate solutions. The following students' responses in verbatim ascertain this conclusion:

FG1 P1: *During the group discussions, we ask what is it that we want to solve and how can we solve it? Then, list the alternative ways on how to solve it then choose the most appropriate one. When I am alone, firstly I try to identify the kind of a problem that I want to solve in the same way. Look for the solutions then choose the best one. It helped me to fully analyse what is it that I want to solve and how can I solve it.*

FG1 P5: *If you have a problem sir, when you are alone if you ask the right questions to yourself like we did in the groups and follow the process on how to come up with the solutions mostly by answering those questions asked...then you will solve the problem, sir. Yes...it was totally different from how I used to solve any problem before.*

FG2 P2: *Before I approach any question, I try to use the skills gained during discussions. Ask myself many questions to analyse the problems, lists all steps in how to solve the problem and find most effective ways to solve the problem.*

Theme 5: Group sessions encouraged/motivated to prepare well for the class

Lack of motivation at the early stages of their study is viewed as a contributing factor by many authors to students failing to pursue programming courses in their later stages of studies (Rahman et al., 2018; Settle et al., 2014). In a typical GIL class, after the introduction of the new topic, students were given fresh challenges/problems to solve as homework or discuss the topic further. Students were expected to participate in discussions in the form of inquiring and answering. Students found this practice motivated them to do the homework and encouraged them to prepare well for the next class, so that they would not feel left behind from the fellow group members. This was evident from their responses such as the following:

FG1 P1: *Group sessions motivated me in such a way to wake up every day and be able to come to the class, because we have got so lot in common and got so much to do. When we are trying to solve the problem, like we discuss first and then see which one is better than other one. So, it was more of like of a competition, but in a good way. So, that motivate us, that motivate me, in particular to be able to come and return.*

Same student went on to say, *It's good, it's exciting and it's also challenging, because obviously everyone is gonna try to be better than someone else. So, people work harder to impress the group basically.*

FG1 P4: *Group works for me sir, they motivate me in a way that, obviously I don't want to be the one that contributes the least. So, it will make me work harder. Then knowing that this certain person works hard, so I have to put in more effort and work harder so that I can have the spotlight. I'm sure they have the same mentality to work harder than me. So, it motivates me in that way. Everyone wants to be a winner. No one wants to be a loser.*

FG2 P4: *It motivated in that everyone in the group debate. In the discussion part. So no one is just sit down and listening. So I will prepare for myself, so that I can add, contribute to the discussions.*

FG2 P2: *It helped a lot because I know I am going to class. I am going to meet other students, that is for them to help me. So I have to go to them and ask the questions. Then you have to contribute.*

FG3 P3: *Getting the answer right and getting back to a position that makes you feel you understand, then when you come to the group you explain to them. That is the motivation - you tell your group what you understand.*

FG4 P2: *Ok, it comes to bit of competition between us as groups. You know if you are in a group with Apiwe, you know Apiwe is good. I will improve myself so that I can be at his standard. I am in a competition with him, yah its good.*

It is evident through these responses from the students that the group sessions motivated them to prepare well and even encouraged them to engage on healthy competition academically while maintaining cordial relationships among themselves.

Theme 6: Changing role of a lecturer in the classroom– From solutions provider to a guide/facilitator

Traditional teaching and learning in the classroom creates a passive learning environment where the teacher/lecturer passes information to students hoping that they would receive the information/knowledge that they are passing on (Kikuchi et al., 2016). The teacher is no longer the 'provider' of information or solutions in GIL, rather a guide who makes sure learners do not deviate from the required task and invokes their thinking by asking thought provoking questions (Khan & O'Rourke, 2004). Though students were not used to this kind of a learning process, their responses as given below show they appreciated this new learning environment and acknowledged this assisted them in improving their own learning skills:

FG1 P3: *Fortunately, our teacher does not spoon feed us. He let us to think on our own and ask us more questions but not give the solutions, and that helped us to analyse the problem better, because we know that we have to come up with a solution.*

FG2 P2: *The lecturer goes around and check what we are doing but never gives us answer. Asked us more questions and at first I couldn't understand this, because we always get answers from teachers. But later I realised that it was good. It forced me to think and find solutions. Now I ask similar questions to myself when I get a problem to solve and get to the answer easily.*

FG4 P2: *I think if we are all confused about certain problem, we will call the lecturer so that he can guide us in the right way and that's where we kind of ok.*

FG4 P1: *Actually he (lecturer) hasn't really given us the answer. He guides.*

FG4 P2: *Yes, he (lecturer) guides us.*

This way of learning was a complete departure from the traditional learning environment the students were so used to. But they appreciated the benefits that this brought to them. They see themselves as the solution generators rather than seeing themselves as the solution seekers.

Theme 7: Helped students cope with the new challenges and expectations of being in HE

Entry-level students enter HE sector not knowing the challenges and expectations of the new environment. This in itself is a major stumbling block in coping with the new environment during the early days of their university life. The non-familiar HE environment coupled with the demands of a non-familiar subjects such as Introduction to Programming courses have the potential to discourage these learners further and add more pressure on them (Jenkins, 2002). Previous studies have identified this as one of the reasons contributing towards high attrition rates among entry-level programming students (D'Souza et al., 2008; Jenkins, 2002). But the collaborative learning environment created through GIL approach has proven to be effective in addressing these challenges. Students' responses as given in verbatim below confirm this:

FG1 P1: *Socialising with people makes you learn more and makes you more comfortable. It helps you with your pressure basically because if your peers are there you will have less pressure.*

FG1 P4: *The fact that we are interdependent with each other help us when we are in groups. So that you know that you need him as well as he needs you. So It helped us to communicate well, try and explain to each other our fears and expectations and strains at varsity. It helped us to be more comfortable with each other.*

FG2 P5: *I for one, when I came from my school straight into the University, I kind of felt that I don't belong here. But having a group to interact with in the class, you just enjoy yourself, because you are*

having a good company. Having a group to help you go through certain things, you don't really succumb to the peer pressure of the things that happen in and outside of the University.

FG2 P4: (GIL environment) helped me because, when I came here the first day, I didn't know anyone. I would just sit here alone, and when the group started, I start chatting to the guys, and get being friends, and now I am confident, and get undepressed easy.

FG3 P4: It happened to me as a surprise. Because when I came here I expected to feel that loneliness for quite some time, because I don't know people, I don't know who to approach. Interacting as a group really helped, because we created some relationships in between the groups and we can talk and interact with our own idea. So it reduced the fear I had.

FG3 P1: Yah when I came, I was bit nervous to communicate with people. But in the groups, everybody is speaking. So there isn't too much pressure. Because after a while, you feel like talking to one of your own people.

FG4 P3: It has lowered the level of pressure you had, because you were like, ok I am on my own.. you just always constantly thinking about it. It worries you and makes you lose focus when you are by yourself. Then in the group, there is less pressure on you. You are more relaxed to work and interact with others.

Theme 8: GIL improved oral communication skills

Programming and software development at the industry/workplace is often not done as a solitary process. There is always a group working on a specific objective but individuals are allocated with sections of the major task (Anewalt& Polack, 2017). So communication skill is an important soft skill a programming graduate must possess (Zarb et al., 2014). Considering the disadvantaged background, the students are hailing from, the graduates coming out of the institutions such as where this study was conducted face communication skills as a major challenge in their success. Students indicated that GIL sessions had not only assisted them in mastering the course content, but also developed them in other areas. They were encouraged to participate in group sessions with 'strangers' who became peers, that in turn gave them confidence in expressing themselves in front of other people. This was evident through the following responses from students:

FG1 P1: It helped a lot in terms of oral and presentation, and being able to listen to each other...being able to express what you feel, because each one of us get a chance to speak what she/he thinks about a particular problem. So, it enables us to communicate with each other, to give each other a chance and be able to communicate well - not having miscommunication or whatsoever.

FG1 P3: It helps in terms of confidence, because in terms of confidence, being confident about what you think about and to debate. I have learned to stand up for something I believed. Now I am able to stand in front of people and talk, without being scared or something.

FG2 P2: I prefer reading than talking. these group discussions helped me a lot. Because now, I have gained confidence, I can talk with people and collaborate with them.

FG3 P3: For some of us English is not our first language. As we engage in our group it improved our communication skills. Some of us are shy, we are not able to speak out. But now we can speak out fluently and could put our ideas across.

FG3 P3: It also improves your listening skills, like when someone talks, you have to pay attention to them and give them the chance to put their ideas across.

FG4 P1: Some of us come here from rural areas. We come here not confident of our English. When we communicate in groups, we speak in English most. So we are more fluent now. Speaking with our friends in a group, when I say some wrong words, obviously they laugh first, then after a while they correct me. No dude, this is not the way you suppose to say, this is supposed to say in this way. In that sense, it influenced my vocabulary, made me more fluent with my English and I can communicate with anyone now.

Most of the students at this university are hail from the rural parts of South Africa with schools that are characterised by lack of facilities both in terms of skilled and experienced teachers and infrastructure due to the legacy of the apartheid system. Students openly admitted that their language proficiency was not up to the standard. Through GIL sessions, they saw themselves improving on their communication skills and gaining confidence in communicating in English which is the language of instruction at the university and at most of their future workplace/s.

Theme 9: Transformation from being an introvert to expressing oneself freely.

Communication and conversations among students themselves are influenced by the personality traits of students such as being an introvert or an extrovert. Studies have shown that extrovert students tend to be more successful than the introverts (Overbaugh& Lin, 2006). Being able to communicate well is an enabler to be successful once these students are at their future workplace since software development industry by nature

involves group work (Anewalt& Polack, 2017). GIL approach in teaching the Introductory Programming course has assisted the introvert students to come out of their shells and express themselves freely. The following responses from students as given below indicate this:

FG1 P2: *I am not talkative. I am a shy kind of a person. This helped me to develop an interest, to educate myself to work and give me a chance to talk Sir.*

FG2 P5: *Well you get different kinds of people, you get people out there, socialising people. Then there are people that are kind of shy. But the way that this group thing had helped us, that everyone became confident in themselves, eventually became comfortable themselves with the group and they were able to project themselves, were able to interact.*

FG2 P4: *From my side, I am a shy person to talk. I get confidence through talking to both group members and then talking to a class. My confidence grew as time goes. I can talk in front of many too.*

FG4 P1: *Some of the people that were reserved at the beginning of the year are now interacting with everyone.*

FG4 P2 (pointing at another student): *I saw him in the beginning of the year, you know he was not like present, he was reserved, he was shy in the way, but now, it's a different story.*

FG4 P3: *that is correct, I was very quiet at the beginning of the year. I didn't like raising my hands and answering questions. Through group interactions, I became more open.*

Conclusion

The terms motivation, confidence and communication are well linked and lead to one goal for students which is success in their academic course. Motivation affects students' success. Receiving a final incentive such as passing a course is an indicator of learners' extrinsic motivation (Winn, 2002). Final pass rate for experimental group (90%) was far better than that obtained by the control group (52%). This indicated that students who participated with the study had a higher level of motivation to do the Introduction to Programming course. This corroborates the findings of a study conducted among mechanical engineering students using GIL approach (Louw, 2012).

Through communication, students learn from each other and acquire different skills and their confidence will grow and become more motivated (Dorneyi&Thurrel, 1994). The qualitative findings from the focus groups proved that the learners were motivated and confident after engaging in this new way of teaching and learning. Students further indicated that the group sessions motivated them to continue with learning programming not only with the Introductory course but also with future advanced programming courses. It was found that when students were more actively involved in the learning process, they learned new concepts easier and understood the work better. This view was corroborated by many researchers who studied on active learning (Charlevoix et al., 2009; De Weck et al., 2003). The following themes that emerged from the focus group interviews indicated that GIL approach resulted in improved confidence, motivation and communication skills among the students:

- a. (GIL approach) generated self-belief and confidence among students to write computer programs that work
- b. Built strong foundation
- c. Grew in confidence to express themselves in front of others
- d. Improved problem solving skills
- e. Groups sessions encouraged / motivated to prepare well for the next class
- f. Changing role of a lecturer in the classroom – From solutions provider to a guide/facilitator
- g. Helped students cope with the new challenges and expectations of being in a HEI
- h. GIL improved oral communication skills
- i. Transformation from being an introvert to expressing oneself freely

Similar researches conducted by other researchers also support the findings of this study (Louw 2012; Shatila, 2007). GIL approach to learning and teaching had significant positive impact over the confidence, motivation and communication skills of students who were enrolled for the Introductory Programming course.

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